

Fatigue Life of Unidirectional Fibre Composites - Comparison of Experimental Data From the Literature With Model Predictions

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Outline

1. Motivation and background
2. Fatigue **limit** – observations of stable fatigue damage
3. Fatigue **limit** – micromechanical model
4. Fatigue **life** – model predictions
5. Fatigue **life** – model predictions comparison against experimental data
6. Outlook - unresolved issues
7. Summary and conclusions

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Motivation and background

Why would a micromechanical model for prediction of fatigue be useful?

- Because many composite structures are subjected to cyclic loads (and risk failing due to fatigue damage)
- Micromechanical models could help the development of improved composites with longer fatigue life (development of fibre, matrix, interface)

Wind turbine rotor blade

Loads acting on the rotor blade

High cycle fatigue

- Estimation of number of load cycles for wind turbine blades

Number of cycles:

- 20 year x 365 days/year x 24 hours/day x 60 min/hour x 10 rotations/min
= 105×10^6 cycles \approx 10^8 cycles

Example of S-N data

Effect of process and fibre architecture

Different composite materials have different fatigue life

[Korkiakoski et al., Int. J. Fatigue, 2016]

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Talreja proposed that the fatigue life diagram with a **fatigue limit** of the composite

"The fatigue limit of the matrix ... is taken as the lower limit..."

Talreja, Proc. R. Soc. Lond., 1981

Gamstedt and Talreja: Below **fatigue limit**: Isolated fibre failure with debonding

Figure 11 Debond growth from a single fibre break in Region III in CF/epoxy ($\epsilon = 0.89\%$).

Figure 12 Debond propagation from a single fibre break in Region III in CF/epoxy ($\epsilon = 0.89\%$).

Goutianos and Peijs: Optical microscopy: Growth of debond crack during cyclic loading

[Goutianos and Peijs, Adv. Comp. Lett., 2001]

Observations: The debond cracks grow in length during cyclic loading, but slow down and stop growing (arrest) after a number of cycles...

van den Heuvel et al.: Raman spectroscopy: Stress in a broken fibre and stress concentrations in its neighbour fibre

Broken fibre →

“With respect to the positions of the stress concentrations, it is observed that one stress concentration is located at the position of the fibre break, and that the other two stress concentrations are located at the end of each debonded zone”

Neighbour fibre →

[Heuvel, Peijs, Young, Comp Sci Techn, 1998]

Key findings from literature on **fatigue limit**

Basis for the micromechanical model

1: A broken fibre induces stress concentration in its neighbour (at fibre break and debond crack tips)

2: The position of the debond crack tip advances during cyclic loading; the growth rate slows down and stop (crack arrest)

3: A decrease in interfacial sliding friction during cyclic loading can give the increase in the debond length

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Model description

- Isolated fibre breaks exist within a UD fibre composite
- Fibres are assumed to be packed in a hexagonal array

Model description

- The stress induced from the debond crack tip to the next fibre

Fracture mechanics crack tip stress field:

The stress induced from the debond crack tip to the next fibre

$$\hat{\sigma}_f^K = 0.435 \frac{E_f}{E_m} \sqrt{\frac{G_c^i E^*}{d^*}} \quad \frac{1}{E^*} = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{1}{E_f} + \frac{1}{E_m} \right)$$

$$\frac{d^*}{r} = \sqrt{\frac{2\pi}{\sqrt{3}V_f}} - 2$$

Fatigue limit expressed in terms of strain

Stress in intact fibre far ahead of debonding:

$$\frac{\sigma_f^+(\bar{\varepsilon}_{fl})}{E_f} = -\Delta\varepsilon^T \frac{(1 - V_f)E_m}{E_c} + \bar{\varepsilon}_{fl}$$

$$\Delta\varepsilon^T = (\alpha_f - \alpha_m)(T - T_0)$$

$$E_c = V_f E_f + (1 - V_f)E_m$$

Fatigue limit eq. :

$$\mathcal{A}_1 \left\{ \frac{\tau_s^c L_0}{E_f r} \left[\left(\frac{\sigma_f^+(\bar{\varepsilon}_{fl}) + \hat{\sigma}_f^K}{\sigma_0} \right)^m + 5 \left(\frac{\sigma_f^+(\bar{\varepsilon}_{fl})}{\sigma_0} \right)^m \right]^{-1} \ln \left(\frac{5}{6} \right) + \frac{\bar{\sigma}_i}{E_c} \right\} - \bar{\varepsilon}_{fl} = 0$$

Non-dimensional parameter:

$$\mathcal{A}_1 = \frac{2\tau_s^c}{(1 + R)\tau_s^c + (1 - R)\tau_s}$$

Debond initiation stress:

$$\frac{\bar{\sigma}_i}{E_c} = \frac{(1 - V_f)E_m}{E_c} \Delta\varepsilon^T + 2\sqrt{\frac{(1 - V_f)E_m}{E_c} \left(\frac{\mathcal{G}_c^i}{E_f r} \right)}$$

[Sørensen and Goutianos, Mechanics of Materials, (2019)]

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Fatigue limit prediction in terms of strain

By varying the parameters fibre and matrix materials:

- Young's modulus

$$E_f, E_m$$

- Radius of the fibre

$$r$$

- Characteristic strength and Weibull modulus

$$\sigma_0(L_0), m$$

By varying the parameters of the composite:

- Fibre volume fraction

$$V_f$$

- Strain mismatch

$$\Delta\varepsilon^T$$

Fatigue limit Vs fibre stiffness and fibre radius

Fatigue limit Vs Weibull parameters

Fatigue limit Vs composite parameters

Fatigue limit Vs matrix stiffness

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Fatigue limit model comparison with literature results

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Uncertainty in models

Model concepts:

- Models are established on the basis of microscale observations
- Fatigue mechanism could be (most likely are) different for different materials systems and different maximum strain levels

Model parameters:

- Values of mechanical microscale parameters are largely unknown
- Microscale parameters should be determined independent from experiments
- Big need for better microscale mechanical testing methods

Measurement of microscale parameters

Fibre properties

- Stiffness and strength properties can be measured by single fibre tensile testing
- Now, commercial automatized single fibre testing equipment is available \Rightarrow large number of fibres can be tested reproducibly
- Issue: Relevant length in composites smaller than measured gauge length

Matrix properties

- Matrix materials can be characterized as bulk materials
- Issues with constraint curing (spacing between fibres about 1 micron)
- On microscale: triaxial stress state \Rightarrow limit yielding?

Measurement of microscale parameters

Interface properties

- No interface test method is perfect
 - microbond tests: evaporation from large surface?
 - single fibre fragmentation tests: embedded fibre must fail first
 - pull-out: small displacement difficult to measure
 - push-out: surface preparation (polishing) can induce debonding
- Concepts for characterisation:
 - shear strength?
 - debonding energy (breakage of chemical bonds)
 - frictional sliding shear stress (slip along debonded interface)

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Summary

- failure of fibres occurs from one broken fibre to its neighbour
- the fibre failure is induced by the stress field of the debond crack tip
- the “delay” is attributed to an increasing debond length during cyclic loading
- an increasing debond length can be attributed to a decreasing interfacial frictional sliding shear stress (due to repeated interface “wear”)

Conclusions

Micromechanical models predicts longer life and higher fatigue limit by:

- decreasing fibre stiffness

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Thank you for your attention!

Any questions/comments...